

TOP 10

Career Orientation and Development books by European authors for University and Academic use

UNLOCKING CAREER SUCCESS

Top Career Orientation & Development Must-Read for Ambitious Professionals

MOTIVATIONAL SPEAKERS

Top 10 Motivational Speakers in the World

career em

CAREER EXPERTS MAGAZINE

TABLE OF CONTENTS

03 Top 10

Career Orientation and Development books by european authors for University and Academic use

05 Unlocking Career Success

Why "Career Orientation A-Z" is a Must-Read for Ambitious Professionals

8 top 10 living

Motivational Speakers in the World Today

CAREER CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND ORIENTATION

TOP 10 Career Orientation and Development books by european authors for University and Academic use

Career development is a crucial step toward personal and professional success. Europe has produced some of the most valuable books to help individuals navigate their career paths, whether in a university or academic setting. Below is a list of the top ten career orientation and development books written by European authors:

1. "The Career Explorer's Journal" - John Lees (UK)

John Lees, one of the leading career experts in the UK, has crafted a unique guide for those looking to explore and plan their career with clarity and achievable goals.

2. "Working Identity: Unconventional Strategies for Reinventing Your Career" - Herminia Ibarra (France)

Professor Herminia Ibarra from INSEAD brings a fresh approach to career development, highlighting the importance of experimentation and pursuing new opportunities to change career directions.

3. "Career Coaching: An Insider's Guide" - Julia Yates (UK)

This book provides practical advice for those who wish to help others develop their careers, covering everything from starting a career as a professional coach to developing effective strategies for success.

Career Orientation A-Z

4. "The Squiggly Career: Ditch the Ladder, Discover Opportunity, Design Your Career" - Helen Tupper & Sarah Ellis (UK)

A guide that reflects the modern career reality, where the path to success is no longer linear but flexible and adaptable. The authors provide tools for navigating a constantly changing job market.

5. "Career Orientation A-Z" - Gentian Jetishi (Kosovo)

Gentian Jetishi's book is an invaluable resource for students and professionals seeking to build a successful career. By combining practical and theoretical approaches to career orientation and skill development, it is a must-read for Albanian-speaking readers and beyond.

6. "Ikigai: The Japanese Secret to a Long and Happy Life" - Hector Garcia & Francesc Miralles (Spain)

While this book focuses on the Japanese concept of Ikigai, Spanish author Francesc Miralles explores how we can build a meaningful life and successful career by discovering what makes us happy.

7. "How to Own the Room: Women and the Art of Brilliant Speaking" - Viv Groskop (UK)

A book that focuses on developing public speaking and confidence, which are essential for success in any career field.

8. "The Pathfinder: How to Choose or Change Your Career for a Lifetime of Satisfaction and Success" - Nicholas Lore (Netherlands)

A deep and comprehensive guide for those seeking their ideal career. Lore includes practical techniques to identify internal skills and interests and align them with career opportunities.

9. "The Science of Getting Rich" - Wallace D. Wattles (UK)

Although this book was written in the early 20th century, its message about personal development and financial success remains relevant in today's world of business and career building

10. "Finding Your Element" - Sir Ken Robinson (UK)

Sir Ken Robinson guides readers in finding and developing what is most important to them—their "element." He emphasizes the importance of following passions to achieve a fulfilled life.

Unlocking Career Success

Why "Career Orientation A-Z" is a Must-Read for Ambitious Professionals

In an era of rapid professional change and evolving job markets, finding clarity in career direction can be daunting. Gentian Jetishi's latest book, "Career Orientation A-Z", addresses this challenge head-on. Tailored for students, educators, and professionals alike, the book stands out for its comprehensive and systematic approach to career development, offering clear steps to achieve career fulfillment.

Jetishi draws on his extensive experience in career management to create a practical guide that not only introduces readers to key career theories but also provides actionable exercises for personal and professional growth. His emphasis on self-assessment, goal setting, and soft skills development positions the book as a key resource for anyone looking to build a lasting and impactful career.

Career Development for the Modern Professional

"Career Orientation A-Z" shines as a career management tool by blending timeless principles with contemporary challenges. The book's focus on building critical thinking, leadership skills, and communication abilities aligns with the needs of the modern workforce, making it a particularly valuable read for professionals seeking to stay competitive. Jetishi's insights into navigating today's job market come from real-world examples, making the content relevant, relatable, and applicable across industries.

For students and early-career professionals, the book offers step-by-step guides for resume building, job searching, and networking, while also incorporating chapters on lifelong learning—critical in today's evolving job landscape.

For more seasoned professionals, "Career Orientation A-Z" offers strategies to master work-life balance, build personal branding, and foster a growth mindset.

A Career Bible for Educators and Trainers

For educators, this book offers more than theory—it provides a solid foundation for curriculum development in career guidance. Teachers will find it easy to incorporate Jetishi's frameworks and exercises into lesson plans, empowering students to make thoughtful, informed career choices. The book's unique models of career planning make it an essential classroom resource.

Career counselors and trainers will appreciate how "Career Orientation A-Z" synthesizes both psychological and sociological theories into practical advice. The book introduces fresh perspectives on career orientation, including Jetishi's focus on aligning personal values with professional goals, making it an essential resource for anyone providing career coaching or mentoring.

Expert Praise for "Career Orientation A-Z"

olivia wilson is making waves with her newest tech launch.

From the perspective of a career expert, Gentian Jetishi's "Career Orientation A-Z" stands out for its clarity, depth, and practical value. By combining research-based insights with hands-on activities, Jetishi has crafted a guide that serves not only as a roadmap for career planning but as an essential reference for personal and professional success.

The book's approach to self-reflection and goal setting ensures readers can take actionable steps toward a more fulfilling career. Moreover, its emphasis on soft skills development is crucial in an era where emotional intelligence, adaptability, and leadership are often as important as technical expertise.

"Career Orientation A-Z" is more than a book—it's a vital resource for anyone serious about their career. Jetishi's approach goes beyond surface-level advice, offering deep insights into the intricacies of career development. Whether you are just starting out, transitioning to a new field, or looking to excel in your current role, this book provides the tools and strategies needed to succeed in today's dynamic job market.

For educators, professionals, and career coaches alike, this book is an invaluable addition to any professional library—one that will inspire, educate, and empower individuals to take charge of their career paths with confidence.

Dive into the transformative journey of 'Career Orientation,' a comprehensive handbook meticulously crafted to guide you through every aspect of your professional growth. From exploring the evolution of career theories to mastering essential thinking skills, crafting compelling resumes, and navigating the job market with confidence, this book offers a roadmap to success. Discover lifelong learning strategies, cultivate meaningful relationships, and access valuable resources for personal and professional fulfillment. Whether you're a seasoned professional or just starting your career, 'Career Orientation' is your go-to companion for unlocking your full potential and building a fulfilling career

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<https://www.alphapublisher.com/abp-gentian-jetishi>

Top 10 Living

Motivational Speakers in the World Today

Motivational speakers are a driving force behind many people's journeys to success. Here's a list of the top 10 living motivational speakers who are actively inspiring audiences across the globe!

1. Tony Robbins

3. Brené Brown

Tony Robbins is perhaps the most famous living motivational speaker. With over 40 years in the personal development space, his energy-packed seminars and books focus on personal empowerment, psychology, and achieving massive success in life and business.

Brené Brown is a research professor and author who speaks on vulnerability, courage, and leadership. Her work has reached global audiences, particularly through her TED Talks and books, encouraging individuals to embrace imperfections and grow stronger.

2. Simon Sinek

Simon Sinek continues to inspire through his groundbreaking work on leadership and motivation, particularly through his Start With Why philosophy. His message resonates across corporate leadership and personal development sectors.

4. Gary Vaynerchuk (Gary Vee)

Gary Vee remains a prominent motivational figure, particularly among entrepreneurs and younger audiences. His unfiltered and high-energy approach motivates people to embrace their passion, work hard, and innovate in today's business landscape.

5. Mel Robbins

Mel Robbins is a leading voice in self-help, famous for her 5 Second Rule, which helps people take immediate action. She continues to motivate individuals globally with her practical advice on overcoming procrastination and self-doubt.

6. Les Brown

Les Brown, though a veteran in motivational speaking, is still active and continues to inspire through his talks and media appearances. His life story, from hardship to success, encourages people to pursue their dreams with passion and resilience.

7. Eric Thomas (ET The Hip Hop Preacher)

Eric Thomas is one of the most passionate and dynamic motivational speakers today. His relatable storytelling and energetic delivery connect deeply with audiences, especially in underserved communities and schools, pushing people to strive for greatness.

8. Jay Shetty

Jay Shetty has become one of the most influential motivational speakers today, thanks to his blend of spiritual wisdom and modern-day practicality. His insights on mindfulness, self-love, and purpose continue to draw large global audiences through his talks and social media.

9. Robin Sharma

Robin Sharma, best known for his work on personal leadership, including The Monk Who Sold His Ferrari, remains an influential speaker. He continues to help people achieve peak performance and lead themselves and others effectively.

10. Trent Shelton

Trent Shelton is a former NFL player turned motivational speaker. Known for his emotional and empowering videos, he addresses personal growth, relationships, and mental well-being, particularly for younger audiences seeking direction and purpose in life. These ten speakers are actively shaping lives with their powerful messages, offering hope, motivation, and practical strategies for success. Their ongoing work continues to inspire millions globally.

Career Orientation A-Z by Gentian Jetishi

Dive into the transformative journey of 'Career Orientation,' a comprehensive handbook...

Alpha Book Publisher

A Book for students, teachers, and trainers

CAREER ORIENTATION A - Z

• By Gentian Jetishi

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Career Orientation A-Z

A Book for students, teachers, and trainers

Dive into the transformative journey of 'Career Orientation,' a comprehensive handbook meticulously crafted to guide you through every aspect of your professional growth. From exploring the evolution of career theories to mastering essential thinking skills, crafting compelling resumes, and navigating the job market with confidence, this book offers a roadmap to success. Discover lifelong learning strategies, cultivate meaningful relationships, and access valuable resources for personal and professional fulfillment. Whether you're a seasoned professional or just starting your career, 'Career Orientation' is your go-to companion for unlocking your full potential and building a fulfilling career.

A BOOK FOR STUDENTS, TEACHERS, AND TRAINERS

CAREER ORIENTATION A - Z

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